

Synthesis of New Local Anaesthetics. Part VII

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Several derivatives of 2-amino-4-arylthiazoles and their hydrochlorides have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activities tested.

In continuation of our previous work¹ 2-amino-4-phenyl-and-4-chloro (*-p*-bromo-, *p*-methyl-, and *m*-nitro)-phenylthiazoles were prepared from the respective acetophenones. These thiazoles were condensed with chloroacetyl chloride to obtain the corresponding chloroacetyl amino compounds. The chloroacetyl amino derivatives were further condensed with morpholine, piperidine, piperazine, and diethylamine. The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activities tested by frog's sciatic plexus method.

A study of pharmacological screening² shows that the hydrochlorides of the 2-amino morpholinoacetyl-4-*m*-nitrophenyl- and 2-aminodiethylaminoacetyl-4-*p*-methyl-phenylthiazoles are the most potent local anaesthetics amongst the compounds prepared.

It is observed that nitro group in phenyl radical attached to 4-position of the thiazole and diethylamino group in side chain enhances the local anaesthetic activity

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-4-substituted Thiazoles.—2-Amino-4-phenyl-, -4(*p*-chloro-, *-p*-bromo-, *m*-nitro)-phenyl-(m.p. 178°) and -4-*p*-methylphenyl (m.p. 130°)-thiazoles were prepared according to the methods of Dodson and King³ and Bhargava *et al.*¹

2-Chloroacetyl amino-4-phenylthiazole.—2-Amino-4-phenylthiazole (7 g.) dissolved in pure dry benzene (50 ml), was taken in a r. b. flask and chloroacetyl chloride (3 ml), dissolved in pure dry benzene (20 ml), was gradually added to it. The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water bath for 1½ hours and benzene was distilled. The residue was first washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water and dried. The product was crystallised from ethanol as a brown solid, m.p. 150°, yield 6.5 g. (Found: N, 11.16; S, 12.87. C₁₁H₉N₂OSCl requires N, 11.09, S, 12.67%).

Similarly chloroacetyl derivatives of 2-amino-[4-*p*-chloro-, 4-*p*-bromo-, nitro-phenyl- (m.p. 168°) and -4-*p*-methylphenyl- (m.p. 150°)-thiazoles were obtained.

1. Bhargava *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1957, **34**, 42; 1960, **37**, 241, 314; 1961, **38**, 167.
2. Bulbring and Wajda, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Therap.*, 1945, **85**, 75.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242.

TABLE I

S.No.	Compounds.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.		% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	2-Mo-4-phenyl T.	105°	Colorless	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	59.4	59.39	5.64	5.61	13.08	13.86	11.02	10.56
2.	2-Mo-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl T.	105°	Pale yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ SCl	53.1	53.34	4.80	4.74	12.25	12.45	9.69	9.48
3.	2-Mo-4- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl T.	130°	Colorless	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Br	47.3	47.12	4.30	4.18	10.71	10.90	8.52	8.37
4.	2-Mo-4- <i>m</i> -nitrophenyl T.	148°	Pale yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	51.81	51.73	4.63	4.50	16.21	16.00	9.42	9.12
5.	2-Mo-4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl T.	86°	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	60.42	60.56	6.11	5.99	13.00	13.24	10.27	10.09
6.	2-Pz-4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl T.	145°	Colorless	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	64.51	64.76	6.73	6.66	13.12	13.33	9.82	10.16
7.	2-Pz-4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl T.	113°	Brown	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₄ S	62.11	62.01	6.41	6.38	17.10	17.02	10.32	9.72
8.	2-Da-4- <i>p</i> -methylphenyl T.	81°	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₃ S	63.21	63.37	6.99	6.93	13.61	13.87	10.33	10.56

Note:— 2-Mo — denotes 2-acetylamino-morpholino.

T — denotes thiazole.

2-Pz — denotes 2-acetylamino-piperidino.

2-Pz — denotes 2-acetylamino-piperazino.

2-Da — denotes 2-acetylamino-diethylamino.

TABLE II

Hydrochlorides.

Compounds, #S.No.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Nitrogen.		%Sulphur.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	180°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	53.11	53.03	5.40	5.30	12.12	12.37	0.66	0.42
2.	214°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ (O ₂ SCl) ₂	48.00	48.12	4.64	4.51	11.40	11.23	8.40	8.55
3.	140°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ SClBr	43.20	43.01	4.11	4.06	10.11	10.03	7.29	7.64
4.	124°	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	46.92	46.81	4.40	4.42	14.41	14.50	8.21	8.32
5.	228°	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	54.80	54.31	5.52	5.55	12.00	11.88	9.40	9.05
6.	204°	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	58.21	58.03	6.11	6.26	12.10	11.95	9.30	9.10
7.	241°	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	56.00	55.91	6.13	6.02	15.11	15.32	9.31	8.73
8.	185°	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	56.48	56.56	6.50	6.48	12.30	12.37	9.61	9.43

* The numbers represent the hydrochlorides of the corresponding compounds named in Table I.

2-Acetylaminomorpholino-4-phenylthiazole.—To 2-chloroacetyl-amino-4-phenylthiazole (5 g.), dissolved in ethanol (absolute, 40 ml) morpholine (1.8 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours on a water bath. Ethanol was recovered and the residue was washed first with sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with water. The product was crystallised from absolute ethanol, m.p. 105°. (Found: C, 59.4; H, 5.64; N, 13.86; S, 11.02. $C_{15}H_{17}O_2N_3S$ requires C, 59.39; H, 5.61; N, 13.86; S, 10.56%).

Similarly 2-acetylmorpholino derivatives of the other thiazoles viz., 2-aminoacetyl-piperzino-, -piperidino-, and -diethylamino-4-*p*-methylphenylthiazoles were prepared. The results are recorded in Table I.

The hydrochlorides of these bases were prepared as usual by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas into the ethereal solution of the bases. The results are mentioned in Table II.

Pharmacological Test.—The hydrochlorides, summarised in Table II, were screened for local anaesthetic activity by frog's sciatic plexus test in the month of April. Two frogs were tested for each compound in 0.1% and 0.2% concentration and the time taken by a given concentration of a local anaesthetic to fail to provoke withdrawal of foot was recorded and compared with that of procaine hydrochloride as a standard substance. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Local anaesthetic activity of the hydrochlorides.

Hydrochlorides of *S. No.	With 0.1% soln. for onset of anaesthesia in		With 0.2% soln. for onset of anaesthesia in	
	0.1N-HCl,	0.2N-HCl,	0.1N-HCl,	0.2N-HCl.
1	8 mins.	9 mins.	5 mins.	6 mins.
2	8	10	6	7
3	9	12	7	8
4	6	8	4	5
5	11	12	9	10
6	10	12	8	9
7	11	12	9	10
8	7	9	4	5
9	10	12	9	11

*The numbers 1-8 represent the compounds stated in Table II and No. 9 represents procaine.

The study of the pharmacological screening shows that the hydrochlorides of 2-acetylaminodiethylamino-4-*p*-methylphenyl- and 2-acetylaminomorpholino-4-*m*-nitrophenyl-thiazoles have the highest local anaesthetic activity amongst the present compounds and requires less time for the onset of anaesthesia than others, although all the compounds are more potent than the standard substance procaine hydrochloride.

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